

Photolysis of Amides and Amines in Sunlight

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In a previous publication Gopala Rao and Dhar (*vide*, p. 617) have shown that amino acids are oxidised in aqueous solution in the presence of air and sunlight with the liberation of ammonia. The view has been given out that the formation of ammonia from amino acids in the soil is, at least in part, a photochemical process, and can take place without the presence of bacteria and fungi, if only sunlight be present.

In the present paper the experimental results on the photolysis of amides and amines in sunlight have been recorded. Our experiments show that amides are first hydrolysed in aqueous solution with the formation of the corresponding ammonium salt, when exposed to sunlight in the presence of photosensitisers like titanium dioxide. There is no reaction in the dark under the experimental conditions. This is unlike the behaviour of animal charcoal which according to Warburg can catalyse the oxidation of amino acids in the dark by oxygen. Further, if a slightly basic substance like calcium carbonate be present, the ammonia of ammonium salt is oxidised to nitrite.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Photo-oxidation of Amides.

The requisite amount of the amide (Merck) was dissolved in sterile water and the solution poured into a sterilised Erlenmeyer flask of pyrex glass containing a definite amount of the photosensitiser, and the flask was then plugged with cotton wool. It was then exposed to sunlight every day from 10 A. M. to 4 P. M.

A definite volume of the solution was withdrawn by a sterile pipette from time to time; and the amount of ammonia obtained was determined by the Folin æration method; the nitrite formed was estimated in another sample of the solution by the Griess-Ilosvay colorimetric method or the iodometric method developed by Gopala Rao and Pandalai (*Analyst*, 1934, 59, 99).

Formamide.—*M*/20-formamide solution (100 c.c.) was exposed to sunlight in a sterile glass flask with 1 g. of calcium carbonate and 0.1 g. of titanium dioxide. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I.

Amount of amido-nitrogen per liter = 700 mg.

Time of exposure.	NH ₃ -N.	Nitrite-N.	Total N.	% decomp.
10 hr.	60 mg./litre	Nil	60.30	8.57
20	125	0.09 mg./litre	125.09	17.87
30	192	0.15	192.15	27.45
50	340	0.21	340.21	48.60

Acetamide.—*M*/20-aqueous solution of acetamide (100 c.c.) was exposed to sunlight in a pyrex glass flask with 1 g. of calcium carbonate and 0.1 g. of titanium dioxide. A definite volume of the solution was withdrawn from time to time and the ammonia and nitrite contents determined. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE II.

Amount of amido-nitrogen per litre = 700 mg.

Time of exposure.	NH ₃ -N.	Nitrite-N.	Total N.	% decomp.
10 hr.	25.0 mg./litre	Nil	25.00	3.57
20	45.3	2.50 mg./litre	47.80	6.83
30	68.25	6.30	74.53	10.65
50	123.61	12.49	135.10	19.44

Benzamide.—*M*/20-solution of benzamide (100 c.c.) was exposed to sunlight in a pyrex glass flask with 1.0 g. of calcium carbonate and 0.1 g. of titanium dioxide. The solution became yellowish-brown after a few hours' exposure. The NH₃-N was estimated by the Folin method and the nitrite-nitrogen by the colorimetric method.

TABLE III.

Time of exposure.	NH ₃ -N.	Nitrite-N.	Total N.	% decomp.
20 hr.	15.00 mg./litre	Nil	15.00	2.14
50	36.00	0.217 mg./litre	36.217	5.17
80	60.00	0.820	60.82	8.69

It will be evident from a comparison of results in Tables I, II and III that the rate of formation of ammonia from benzamide is much slower than from acetamide or formamide.

Urea.—*M*/20-aqueous solution of urea (100 c.c.) was exposed to sunlight in a pyrex glass flask with 1g. of calcium carbonate and 0.1g. titanium dioxide. The ammoniacal nitrogen was estimated by the Folin method and the nitrite nitrogen by the colorimetric method. The following results show that urea is ammonified and nitrified quite readily.

TABLE IV.

Amount of amido-nitrogen per litre=1400 mg.

Time of exposure.	NH ₃ -N.	Nitrite-N.	Total N.	% decomp.
10 hr.	25.00 mg./litre	1.50 mg./litre	26.5	1.89
20	47.80	2.30	50.1	3.58
40	90.32	8.40	98.72	7.05

Oxamide and succinimide.—*M*/20-aqueous solutions of oxamide and succinimide (100 c.c. each) were exposed to sunlight for 50 hours with 1.0 g. of calcium carbonate and 0.1 g. of titanium dioxide. The results are as follows.

TABLE V

Substance.	NH ₃ -N.	Nitrite-N.	Total N.	% decomp.
Succinimide	64.85 mg./litre	1.2 mg./litre	66.068	9.438
Oxamide	50.44	3.17	52.61	7.516

Phthalimide.—*M*/20-aqueous solution (100 c.c.) was exposed to sunlight with 1.0 g. of calcium carbonate and 0.1 g. of the photosensitiser, titanium dioxide. After a few hours' exposure to sunlight the solution assumed an yellow colour. Ammonia was slowly formed and no nitrite could be detected even on exposure for 50 hours.

TABLE VI.

Time of exposure.	NH ₃ -N.	Nitrite-N per litre.	Total N.	% decomp.
50 hr.	25.22 mg./litre	Nil	25.22	3.6

It will be seen from the results recorded in the foregoing pages that aromatic amides and imides decompose much less readily than the aliphatic ones. Benzamide ammonifies much slower than formamide or acetamide.

Among the aliphatic, the amides of monobasic acids decompose more quickly than those of dibasic acids.

Photo-oxidation of Amines.

Methylamine.—*M/5*-aqueous solution of methylamine (200 c.c.) was exposed to sunlight with 0.4 g. of ZnO for 40 hours. Formaldehyde, methyl alcohol and ammonium nitrite were detected in the reaction mixture. The first stage of the reaction appears to be one of hydrolysis.

This is followed by oxidation of ammonia to nitrite and of methyl alcohol to formaldehyde.

Ethylamine.—When treated in exactly the same manner ethylamine was found to yield ethyl alcohol, acetaldehyde and ammonium nitrite. As in the former case the first stage of the reaction appears to be a case of hydrolysis, represented by the equation,

This was followed by the oxidation of ammonia to nitrite and of ethyl alcohol to acetaldehyde.

Dimethylamine yielded formaldehyde and ammonium nitrite when exposed to sunlight in the presence of zinc oxide.

Aniline.—200 C.c. of distilled water with a quantity of pure aniline calculated to make the mixture *M/5* concentration were exposed in a glass flask to sunlight for 40 hours with 0.4 g. of ZnO. After a few hours' exposure the solution assumed a deep brown colour, and in course of time deposited a brown resinous mass. The amount of nitrite formed was small.

Dimethylaniline when treated in the above manner turned brown, but no nitrite was formed.

The following table gives the amount of nitrite formed in each case.

TABLE VII.

200 C.c of *M/5*-amine in water + 0.4 g. of ZnO exposed to sunlight for 40 hours.

Substance.	Amount of nitrite-N.
Methylamine	35.83 mg./litre
Ethylamine	22.96
Diethylamine	15.56
Aniline	0.28
Dimethylaniline	Nil

From the foregoing results it will be evident that the aliphatic amines are more readily oxidised to nitrite than the aromatic ones. Among the aliphatic amines, the smaller the number of carbon atoms the greater is the tendency for the decomposition.

DISCUSSION.

In our previous publication we have shown that amino acids are oxidised photochemically in aqueous solution, when exposed to sunlight in the presence of photosensitisers like titanium dioxide with the liberation of ammonia. In the present paper we have shown that amides also undergo photochemical oxidation when exposed to sunlight in the presence of photosensitisers like titanium dioxide or zinc oxide, with the ultimate formation of ammonium nitrite. Thus it appears that diverse nitrogenous compounds decompose in the presence of sunlight and air with the formation of ammonia and nitrite.

In the soil nitrogenous compounds undergo similar changes and it is believed that these changes are brought about by the activities of the micro-organisms of the soils, which are specific in their action. The ammonifying organisms of the soil liberate ammonia from the complex nitrogenous compounds, and the ammonia will then be oxidised by the nitrifying bacteria. Now it is interesting to note that sunlight alone can also accomplish all these changes. Hence, we believe that the process of ammonification and nitrification of nitrogenous compounds in the soil may be mainly photochemical in tropical countries, taking place under the influence of sunlight without the interference of bacteria.

